

A study on pH affecting on *Sclerotium rolfsii* causing Root rot on Chilli

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ABSTRACT

The chilli rot is one of the most destructive diseases caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii* in fields. The pathogen is well known. The mycelial growth and sclerotia production of *Sclerotium rolfsii* is influenced by many factors including pH. The influence of different pH levels on growth and production of sclerotia was studied by poisoning food technique. In the present studied citrate-phosphate buffer solution with pH values ranging from 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, .5.5, 6.0, 6.5 and 7.0 were used. The total and average radial growth observed after every 24 hours interval and recorded. The lowest radial growth 55.00 mm and was at recorded at 7.0 pH followed by 3.0 pH level with 70.2 mm after 72 hours of incubation periods. Among all pH levels the highest radial growth were found as 88.33mm on both 4.5 & 5.0 pH levels.

Keywords- *Sclerotium rolfsii*, pH, Scleroia, Radial mycelial growth

INTRODUCTION

Vegetables crop can be infected by more than many pathogens and among all these the soil borne pathogen The *Sclerotium rolfsii* causing root rot in that chili are gaining more importance as they responsible for heavy yield losses. The *Sclerotium rolfsii* is a soil borne pathogen of very aggressive nature, it causes considerable damage to this fungus. The *Sclerotium rolfsii* occurs in diverse soil, has a very wide host range and worldwide distribution (Punja, 1985). These pathogen exhibit variation in their morphological biological and pathogenic variation are known in many fungal pathogens (Adiver, 2006) & as such detailed investigation was carried out on the variation with regards to morphological variation over the different pH on the isolates.

The pathogen is one of the most destructive and common pathogens of chili crop causing root rot disease in fields, the local growers suffered a lot every year. The environmental factor such as incubation periods,

temperature and pH etc. not only influences the growth and sporulation of pathogens (Mishra and Hoque, 1962; Mathur and Sorbhoy, 1976; Sharma and Kaushal, 1979; Khan and quazi, 2010). The *Sclerotium rolfii* Sacc. Teleomorph: (*Cortieium rolfii* Curzi) is a serious soil borne pathogenic fungus and harm to many crops which are economically valuable in most of the tropical and sub-tropical region of the world (Aycock, 1966). It also causes serious disease on other crops, it has a wide host range (Talukder, 1974). The mycelia growth and sclerotia production of this fungus is influence by many factors including pH, temperature, individual nutrients and volatile compound like ethanol and C/N ratio Devi, et al., 1999; Prithiviraj, et al., 2000; Linderman, and Gilbert, 1973).

On this background the present work was undertaken to study the influence / effect of culture pH (hydrogen ion concentration) on the mycelia growth and sclerotia production of *Sclerotium rolfii* sacc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The influence of different pH levels on growth and production of sclerotia was studied by poisoning food technique (Dhingra and Sinclair 1985). Growth variation at different pH levels / the influence of different pH levels on the growth of the pathogenic fungus *Sclerotium rolfii* was studied. The nine different pH levels studied from 3.0 to 7.0 were adjusted to the pH potato dextrose agar medium. This was done before autoclaving with help of buffers i.e. Citrate-Phosphate buffer by using the pH paper. These pH adjusted medium were poured into petriplates, inoculated and incubated for 72 hours for growth variation studies and fifteen days for sclerotia

production/ formation studies. The growth of mycelium recorded after every 24 hours till 72 hours. In the present Citrate-Phosphate buffer solution with pH values ranging from 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0, 6.5 and 7.0 were taken in 100ml conical flask. The 4-5 days old culture grown in potato dextrose agar medium was cut by (flame) sterilized 4mm cork borer. The inoculated petriplates were kept in the incubator for 72 hours for observe radial growth and sclerotia formation till fifteen days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present result an attempt for study has been made to understand the influence of pH revealed in Table 1,2,3, Figure 1 and Graph 1,2. The data present in above table, Figure, and Graph, gave detailed information about radial growth and formation of sclerotia of *Sclerotium rolfii*. The *Sclerotium rolfii* growth was measured over a pH range 3.0 to 7.0 (at 0.5 intervals distance) levels. The low radial growth of pathogen recorded at 7.0 pH level 55mm (average value) followed by at 3.0 pH level and 3.5 pH level with 70.4mm and 71.33mm (average values) respectively. The radial growth was found at 7.0, which was statically different from all pH levels (Sarker, B.C & et al. 2013). Radial growth at pH level 3.0, 3.5, 6.0, 6.5 was statically similar with little radial growth differences that are 70.4, 71.33, 78.00 & 78.25 values are (average of total three replicates). In all the pH levels the highest radial growth were found at pH 4.5 & 5.0 about same 88.33mm (values are average of triplicates). The wide range of pH with optimum near 6.0 for the growth of various isolates of *Sclerotium rolfii* have been reported by Aycock, (1966), Narasimhan (1969), Sharma and Kaushal (1979) & Punja (1984).

Table 1: Effect of different pH levels on the radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfii*.

pH Levels	Total measured After of	radial In	Growth Mm Interval
	24 hours	following 24 hours	Hours
3.0	134	262	352
3.5	139	290	428
4.0	146	259	403
4.5	101	310	503
5.0	155	300	500
5.5	125	291	565
6.0	81	182	313
6.5	123	268	390
7.0	27	81	165

*values are totals of triplicate.

Table 2: Effect of different pH levels on the average total radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

pH Levels	Average measured	Radial In	Growth Mm
	After	Following Hours	Interval
	24 hours	48 hours	72 hours
3.0	22.33	43.66	70.2
3.5	23.16	48.33	71.33
4.0	24.33	51.8	80.6
4.5	16.83	51.66	88.33
5.0	25.83	50	88.33
5.5	25.83	48.5	80.71
6.0	20.25	45.5	78.25
6.5	20.5	44.66	78.00
7.0	9	27	55

*values are average totals of triplicate.

Table 3: The effect of pH on sclerotia formation, color and distribution in petriplates.

pH Levels	Total	Average Color number of sclerotia			Distribution of Sclerotia		
		Tan brown	Black	White	Center	Middle	Periphery
3.0		1.75	7	15	+	+	+
3.5		1.66	16.8	8.833	+	+	-
4.0		1.33	12.33	18.33	+	+	+
4.5		2.33	19.66	32.83	+	+	+
5.0		1.6	14.66	19	+	+	+
5.5		2.83	15.16	20.5	+	+	+
6.0		4.25	16.75	35	+	+	+
6.5		3	26.2	35	+	+	+
7.0		0	20	307	+	+	+

*values are average of triplicate.

Figure 01: The figure of effect of different pH levels on radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

Graph 1: Effect of different pH levels on radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

Graph 2: Effect of different pH levels on average radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

Graph 3: Effect of different pH levels on sclerotia color and white basidiospore formatted in *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

(Decreasing pH levels)

→7.0<6.5<5.5<5.0=4.5>4.0>3.5>3.0 ←(increasing pH levels)

(Increasing growth)

→55<78.00<78.25<80.71<88.33=88.33>80.60>71.33>72.02 ←(Decreasing growth)

The intensity of sclerotial was slowly affected by increases or decreases the pH level (Ansari and Agnihotri, 200; Misra and Haque 1962).

In the present studies an attempt was made to evaluate the influence of pH ranging from 3.0 to 7.0 (at 0.5 level intervals) on the radial growth and formation of sclerotia of *Sclerotium rolfsii* observed from table 1,2, Figure 1 and Graph 1-2. The lowest radial growth 55.00mm observed at 7.0 pH level. The increasing in at pH levels 3.0 to 5.0 or 3.0<3.5<4.0<4.5<5.0. At 4.5 and 5.0 pH levels, the maximum radial growth 88.33mm of *Sclerotium rolfsii* was recorded.

These result of mycelia growth in present study, agree with the findings of Richharia (1984), who has reported that pH at 5.0 was the optimum for mycelial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

CONCLUSION

The influence of pH on mycelial growth and production of sclerotia of *Sclerotium rolfsii* of *Sclerotium rolfsii* causing root rot in vegetables has been show from results, tables, graphs and figures. The *Sclerotium rolfsii* is a soil born plant pathogen of worldwide importance with a very extensive host range including more than 500 plant species that is why the physical factor like pH studies helps us to improve control management. The result gave conclusion that maximum radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* were found at 4.5 and 5.0 pH with 88.33mm mycelia growth. The least radial growth founded 7.0 pH with 55mm and 3.0 with 70.2mm after 72 hours of incubation periods.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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